

Supplementary Materials

Sensitivity of a model oscillator to shifts in the voltage-dependence of one or more ionic currents

Ian Huang¹, Leandro M. Alonso¹, Eve Marder¹

¹Volen Center and Biology Department, Brandeis University, Waltham, MA 02454, USA

Correspondence: L.M. Alonso (lalonso@brandeis.edu), E. Marder (marder@brandeis.edu)

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Supplemental Methods: Voltage Trace Characterization

To characterize the model’s activity, we extracted several features from the voltage traces, including individual spike properties and rhythmic burst dynamics. We quantified the peak and trough amplitudes (min/max voltage), the spike frequency, and the number of spikes per burst. Additionally, we measured burst frequency, burst duration, and duty cycle. Finally, we classified the overall activity as tonic, bursting, or quiescent.

Table 1: Voltage trace measurements for all panels in Figure 1. Burst duration is reported as 0 for tonic firing; N/A indicates metric is not applicable.

Panel	E_K (mV)	$\Delta V_{1/2}$ (mV)	Pattern	Max V (mV)	Min V (mV)	Burst Freq (Hz)	Burst Dur (s)	Duty Cycle	Spikes/Burst	Spike Freq (Hz)
B1	-80	0	Bursting	+50	-58	1.0	0.32	0.31	9	9
B2	-80	-5	Bursting	+50	-62	1.0	0.08	0.08	4	4
B3	-80	-10	Bursting	+50	-57	0.9	0.08	0.07	4	4.4
C1	-56	0	Tonic	+47	-50	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	48
C2	-56	-5	Bursting	+50	-51.2	2.0	0.14	0.28	10	20
C3	-56	-10	Bursting	+50	-51.1	1.25	0.10	0.12	9	11.2

Table 2: Voltage trace measurements for all panels in Figure 2. Burst duration is reported as 0 for tonic firing; N/A indicates metric is not applicable.

Panel	Condition	Pattern	Max V (mV)	Min V (mV)	Burst Freq (Hz)	Burst Dur (s)	Duty Cycle	Spikes/Burst	Spike Freq (Hz)
i	Control	Bursting	+40	-70	1.0	0.38	0.38	10	10.9
ii	Control (shifted)	Bursting	+40	-65	1.0	0.13	0.13	5	5
iii	High [K ⁺]	Tonic	+40	-50	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	48
iv	High [K ⁺] (shifted)	Bursting	+40	-51	2.0	0.17	0.34	10	20

Table 3: Voltage trace measurements for panel C in Figure 4. Burst duration is reported as 0 for tonic firing; N/A indicates metric is not applicable.

Panel	Condition	Pattern	Max V (mV)	Min V (mV)	Burst Freq (Hz)	Burst Dur (s)	Duty Cycle	Spikes/Burst	Spike Freq (Hz)
C-i	Control	Bursting	+50	-67	1.0	0.38	0.38	9	9
C-ii	Early High [K ⁺]	Tonic	+48	-49	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	48
C-iii	Late High [K ⁺]	Bursting	+50	-51	2.1	0.19	0.39	12	25
C-iv	Early Wash	Bursting	+50	-67	1.2	0.16	0.19	6	7.3

Table 4: Voltage trace measurements for all panels in Figure 5. Burst duration is reported as 0 for tonic firing; N/A indicates metric is not applicable.

Panel	Condition	Pattern	Max V (mV)	Min V (mV)	Burst Freq (Hz)	Burst Dur (s)	Duty Cycle	Spikes/Burst	Spike Freq (Hz)
A-i	Control	Bursting	+50	-67	1.0	0.37	0.37	9	9
A-ii	Early High [K ⁺]	Tonic	+48	-49	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	44
A-iii	Late High [K ⁺]	Bursting	+50	-50	2.1	0.24	0.51	16	34.0
A-iv	Early Wash	Bursting	+50	-67	1.2	0.18	0.22	11	13.7
B-i	Control	Bursting	+50	-67	1.0	0.37	0.37	9	9
B-ii	Early High [K ⁺]	Tonic	+48	-49	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	44
B-iii	Late High [K ⁺]	Bursting	+50	-50	2.3	0.21	0.46	11	25.5
B-iv	Early Wash	Bursting	+20	-61	1.1	0.12	0.14	5	6

Table 5: Voltage trace measurements for all panels in Figure 6. Burst duration is reported as 0 for tonic firing; N/A indicates metric is not applicable.

Panel	Condition	Pattern	Max V (mV)	Min V (mV)	Burst Freq (Hz)	Burst Dur (s)	Duty Cycle	Spikes/Burst	Spike Freq (Hz)
A-i	Control	Bursting	+36	-62.5	1.0	0.37	0.37	21	21
A-ii	Early High [K ⁺]	Tonic	+22.5	-37.5	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	52.6
A-iii	Late High [K ⁺]	Bursting	+36	-50	2.3	0.17	0.38	15	34
A-iv	Early Wash	Bursting	+36	-63.7	1.2	0.18	0.22	12	15
B-i	Control	Bursting	+47.5	-65.4	1.0	0.12	0.12	6	6.1
B-ii	Early High [K ⁺]	Tonic	+41	-50	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	59
B-iii	Late High [K ⁺]	Bursting	+47.5	-57.7	1.8	0.21	0.38	14	25.9
B-iv	Early Wash	Bursting	+47.5	-65.4	0.8	0.12	0.10	5	4.3
C-i	Control	Bursting	+48.7	-79.8	1.2	0.27	0.31	12	14
C-ii	Early High [K ⁺]	Tonic	+40.8	-49.8	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	41.6
C-iii	Late High [K ⁺]	Bursting	+48.7	-52.6	1.4	0.21	0.30	12	17.2
C-iv	Early Wash	Bursting	+48.7	-77.6	1.3	0.16	0.21	8	10.4

Table 6: Voltage trace measurements for panel C in Figure 7 (zoomed traces). Burst duration is reported as 0 for quiescent activity; N/A indicates metric is not applicable.

Panel	Condition	Pattern	Max V (mV)	Min V (mV)	Burst Freq (Hz)	Burst Dur (s)	Duty Cycle	Spikes/Burst	Spike Freq (Hz)
C-i	Control	Bursting	+23.8	-50.1	1.4	0.09	0.13	6	8.5
C-ii	Early High [K ⁺]	Single-spoke burst	+23.8	-52.2	2.6	0	0	1	2.6
C-iii	Late High [K ⁺]	Bursting	+19	-49.1	2.9	0.05	0.15	5	14.7
C-iv	Early Wash	Bursting	+19	-53.1	1.0	0.05	0.05	2	2.1